

GEOLOGICAL AND MINERALOGICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURAL CONTROL ON GROUNDWATER PRODUCTIVITY IN A TECTONICALLY COMPLEX MINING AREA: THE AKSSU–ZHOLYMBET CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Groundwater productivity in mining areas often shows strong spatial heterogeneity that cannot be explained only by borehole depth or lithology. This complicates hydrogeological assessment, dewatering design, and water management at mine sites. This study evaluates structural control on groundwater productivity using the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area (Northern Kazakhstan) as a case study. The analysis uses data from sixteen hydrogeological boreholes (23–120 m), including pumping test results, static water levels, and borehole spatial distribution. Discharge values range from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s, including boreholes of similar depth located close to each other. No clear relationship between depth and discharge is observed, suggesting that depth-based productivity criteria are limited in the studied conditions. The variability is interpreted as an effect of structural heterogeneity, where faults and fracture zones provide preferential groundwater flow pathways. The results may support improved inflow prediction and more robust dewatering design in structurally complex mining settings.

Keywords: groundwater productivity; fractured aquifer; faults; structural control; pumping test; mine dewatering; Akssu–Zholymbet; Northern Kazakhstan.

Introduction

Hydrogeological conditions in mining areas are characterized by high spatial heterogeneity and complex groundwater flow structures, which significantly complicate the assessment of groundwater inflows, the design of dewatering systems, and groundwater resource management. In both open-pit and underground mining, groundwater flow is controlled by a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including lithological composition, tectonic disturbance of the rock mass, fracture intensity, and stress changes induced by mining activities[1,3,6,11].

One of the key features of hydrogeological systems in mining areas is the pronounced variability of groundwater productivity. Numerous studies show that boreholes drilled to similar depths within the same mining site may exhibit discharge differences of one to two orders of magnitude[2,7]. Such variability indicates the limited applicability of simplified depth-oriented approaches, in which drilling depth is considered the primary indicator of groundwater potential.

In tectonically complex areas composed mainly of fractured and fractured–porous aquifers, groundwater flow is primarily controlled by secondary permeability associated with faults, fracture zones, and fracture networks. These structural elements form preferential flow paths that localize groundwater flow within zones of

limited thickness but high permeability [5,9]. As a result, borehole depth ceases to be a reliable indicator of productivity, and groundwater inflows exhibit a distinctly heterogeneous pattern.

Structural control is particularly pronounced in mining areas located within structural–metallogenic zones. Such zones are typically characterized by intense tectonic disturbance and well-developed fracture systems related to both regional faults and local structures associated with ore-forming processes. Under these conditions, structural elements exert a dominant influence on the distribution of hydraulic properties and the formation of high-productivity groundwater zones[6,10].

The relevance of studying structural control on groundwater productivity is confirmed by field hydrogeological investigations conducted in the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area. Based on drilling and pumping test data from sixteen hydrogeological boreholes with depths ranging from 23 to 120 m, discharge values were found to vary from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s, including boreholes of comparable depth located in close proximity. The absence of a clear relationship between borehole depth and discharge indicates the dominant role of structural factors over depth and lithological parameters.

The objective of this study is to assess the role of structural factors in controlling groundwater productivity in the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area based on drilling and pumping test data.

The specific tasks of the study include:

- analysis of the relationship between borehole depth and discharge;
- assessment of the spatial variability of groundwater productivity;
- comparison of hydrogeological characteristics between the North and South pits;
- interpretation of observed patterns considering the structural and tectonic features of the area.

The results aim to substantiate the leading role of structural control in groundwater flow formation and can be applied in hydrogeological investigations and dewatering system design in structurally complex mining areas.

Literature Review

Recent studies of hydrogeological conditions in mining areas increasingly emphasize the key role of structural factors in controlling groundwater flow and aquifer productivity. In contrast to classical models assuming relatively homogeneous vertical distributions of hydraulic properties, contemporary research demonstrates that in fractured and tectonically disturbed rock masses, groundwater flow is governed primarily by secondary permeability associated with faults and fracture systems.

Several recent studies show that borehole discharge variability in mining areas can reach one to two orders of magnitude even at comparable drilling depths. For example, Rózkowski et al. [11], based on an open-pit mine case study, demonstrated that groundwater inflow distribution is controlled not by the depth of aquifer interception but by the spatial configuration of high-permeability zones associated with tectonic structures. Similar conclusions were drawn by Ca and Laar [2], who highlighted the limitations of depth-based approaches in groundwater inflow prediction and mine water management.

Considerable attention has been paid to methods for identifying and quantitatively assessing structural control on groundwater flow. The application of geophysical methods, including electrical resistivity tomography, aeromagnetic, and electromagnetic surveys,

enables the detection of fracture zones and high-permeability pathways that play a decisive role in groundwater productivity. It has been demonstrated that electrical resistivity tomography significantly improves the assessment of spatial groundwater heterogeneity in fractured aquifers [7]. More recent studies by [6] confirmed the effectiveness of integrating ground-based geophysical methods for characterizing near-surface aquifers within active mining sites.

Advances in numerical and analytical modeling also reflect a shift from simplified depth-based criteria toward explicit consideration of structural heterogeneity [4]. Modern groundwater flow models in fractured media incorporate parameters describing fracture network connectivity, permeability anisotropy, and stress-dependent behavior. Preisig et al. [10] established the basis for regional flow modeling in fractured aquifers accounting for stress conditions, while later studies [4,12] further developed these approaches and emphasized the necessity of comprehensive structural characterization.

Structural control is particularly significant in areas associated with structural–metallogenic zones, where ore-forming processes are accompanied by intense tectonic deformation. Such zones often coincide with areas of increased hydraulic conductivity and localized groundwater inflows, which is critical for mine hydrogeological assessment and inflow risk management [6,8].

However, despite these advances, field-based evidence from structurally metallogenic zones remains limited, particularly with respect to quantitative assessment of groundwater productivity variability at the scale of active mining operations.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on the results of field hydrogeological investigations conducted within the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area. The dataset includes drilling and operational data from sixteen hydrogeological boreholes located in the North and South pits. Borehole depths range from 23 to 120 m, covering the upper and middle portions of the aquifer system within the studied rock mass.

The locations of the hydrogeological boreholes in the North and South pits are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Location of the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area showing the distribution of hydrogeological boreholes within the North and South pits

For each borehole, data on design and actual depth, casing and screen construction, static groundwater levels, and results of trial and pumping tests were used. Additional information included borehole spatial coordinates and results of limited hydrochemical analyses of groundwater samples.

Drilling Methods and Borehole Construction

Hydrogeological boreholes were drilled using standard techniques applied in engineering and hydrogeological investigations under open-pit mining conditions. Casing pipes with diameters of 127 and 159 mm were used depending on design conditions and expected productivity. Borehole construction included screened intervals positioned within inferred water-bearing and fractured zones.

Actual borehole depths generally corresponded to design values, ensuring data comparability. Screen placement was guided by lithological logs and observed indications of increased fracturing during drilling.

Pumping Tests

Groundwater productivity was assessed through trial and pumping tests conducted to determine borehole discharge, groundwater level response, and preliminary hydraulic properties of the rock mass. Measured discharge values ranged from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s, reflecting pronounced spatial heterogeneity. Static groundwater levels were recorded prior to pumping and used for comparative analysis between different parts of the mining area.

Hydrochemical Analysis

Groundwater samples were collected from all boreholes for limited chemical analysis. The hydrochemical data were used to characterize groundwater

composition and assess genetic uniformity within the study area. The results showed no pronounced hydrochemical anomalies that could explain the observed discharge variability, allowing the analysis to focus on structural and hydrodynamic factors.

Spatial and Comparative Analysis

Comparative and spatial analyses were applied to assess the influence of structural factors on groundwater productivity. Relationships between borehole depth and discharge were evaluated, as well as differences in productivity between the North and South pits. Particular attention was paid to cases of significant discharge variability at comparable depths and close spatial proximity.

Correlation analysis was used to test for statistical relationships between borehole depth and discharge. The absence of a stable correlation was interpreted as evidence of dominant structural control over depth-related and lithological factors.

Interpretation Approach

Result interpretation is based on the concept of structurally controlled groundwater flow, whereby aquifer productivity in fractured and tectonically disturbed rock masses is governed by the configuration of faults, fracture zones, and their hydraulic connectivity. Hydrogeological data were compared with the general structural–tectonic setting of the area to qualitatively assess the role of structural elements in forming zones of increased or reduced groundwater productivity.

Results

Analysis of drilling and pumping test data from the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area yielded hydrogeological information for sixteen boreholes located within the North and South pits. Borehole depths range from

23 to 120 m, and actual depths generally correspond to design values.

Static groundwater levels range from 13.1 to 24.6 m, indicating relatively similar hydrodynamic conditions across the study area. Despite this, borehole discharge values show high variability.

Pumping test results indicate discharge values ranging from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s. The highest discharges were recorded in individual boreholes in both pits, while several boreholes exhibit minimal inflows at comparable depths.

Notably, boreholes drilled to depths of 60–100 m show discharge differences of one to two orders of magnitude, indicating strong spatial heterogeneity of aquifer properties and the absence of a direct depth–productivity relationship.

Comparison of discharge values with borehole depths shows no consistent linear or monotonic relationship. In several cases, shallow boreholes exhibit

higher discharges than deeper ones, confirming the limited applicability of depth-based productivity criteria.

Comparative analysis between the North and South pits reveals differences in discharge ranges and hydrodynamic characteristics. In the North pit, both high- and low-discharge boreholes occur at similar depths, indicating strong local heterogeneity. A similar pattern is observed in the South pit, although discharge values tend to cluster within moderate ranges, with isolated high-discharge anomalies.

Hydrochemical analysis indicates relative compositional uniformity of groundwater across the study area. No chemical anomalies were identified that could account for the observed discharge variability.

The main hydrogeological parameters of the boreholes, including depth, discharge, and static water level, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.

Summary of borehole depth, discharge and static water levels

Borehole ID	Pit	Depth (m)	Static water level (m)	Discharge Q (L/s)
SKT-01	North	120.0	22.47	5.5
SKT-04	North	120.0	21.25	0.8
SKT-11	North	60.0	21.10	1.8
SKT-01n	North	80.0	22.71	0.5
SKT-02	North	91.3	18.49	3.7
SKT-08	North	91.0	23.13	1.5
SKT-10	North	90.0	17.06	0.1
SKT-03	North	87.0	22.01	0.1
SKT-06	South	78.0	20.95	0.89
SKT-07	South	90.0	24.57	0.25
SKT-12	South	61.0	18.36	0.1
SKT-14	South	80.0	24.03	0.4
SKT-09	South	60.0	13.07	2.56
SKT-13	South	51.7	17.61	1.6
SKT-05	South	23.0	–	–
HDR-12-1	South	77.0	–	20.0

Notes:

- “–” indicates unavailable measurements.
- Borehole depths correspond to actual drilled depths.
- Discharge values obtained from trial and pumping tests.

Figure 2 illustrates the absence of a clear relationship between borehole depth and discharge.

Figure 2 — Q -Depth (Discharge vs depth)

Figure 3 highlights the pronounced spatial heterogeneity of groundwater discharge within the study area.

Figure 3 - Spatial distribution of groundwater discharge (annotated extremes)

These results provide an empirical basis for the subsequent discussion of the role of structural factors in controlling groundwater productivity in the Akssu-Zholymbet mining area.

The conceptual representation of structurally controlled groundwater flow is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Conceptual model of structurally controlled groundwater flow
The drilling timeline of the hydrogeological boreholes during 2025–2026 is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 - Drilling timeline of boreholes (2025–2026)

Discussion

The results clearly demonstrate that groundwater productivity in the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area is not controlled by borehole depth. This is evident from the discharge–depth relationship (Fig. 2), where discharge values vary from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s at comparable depths between 50 and 120 m. The absence of a clear correlation indicates the limited applicability of depth-oriented hydrogeological approaches.

Such behavior is typical of tectonically disturbed and fractured rock masses, where groundwater flow is

controlled by secondary permeability rather than stratigraphic position. Boreholes intersecting fracture zones or faults exhibit significantly higher discharges than nearby boreholes of similar depth located outside these structures.

The spatial distribution of discharge values (Fig. 3) highlights a pronounced mosaic pattern of groundwater productivity. Boreholes located in close proximity show sharply contrasting discharge values, excluding regional hydrodynamic conditions as the sole explanation.

Localized high-productivity zones, such as borehole HDR-12-1 with a discharge of 20.0 L/s, indicate the presence of structurally controlled flow paths likely associated with fault zones or areas of intense fracturing. Similar patterns are observed in the North pit, where discharge values vary by one to two orders of magnitude at depths of 90–120 m.

Comparison between the North and South pits shows that both areas exhibit high spatial heterogeneity, although the distribution and intensity of high-discharge zones differ. These differences may reflect variations in fault density, orientation, and the degree of mining-induced disturbance.

The findings have important practical implications. First, reliance on borehole depth as the primary predictor of groundwater inflow may lead to significant errors. Second, the observed heterogeneity underscores the need for detailed structural analysis in dewatering system design.

Limitations and Future Research

The interpretation of structural control in this study is primarily qualitative and based on spatial analysis of borehole depth and discharge. Future research should incorporate detailed structural–geological mapping, geophysical investigations, and numerical groundwater flow modeling to quantitatively assess the contribution of individual fault and fracture systems.

Conclusion

Analysis of data from sixteen hydrogeological boreholes in the Akssu–Zholymbet mining area shows high spatial variability in groundwater productivity, with discharge values ranging from 0.1 to 20.0 L/s at comparable depths.

The absence of a clear depth–discharge relationship (Fig. 2) demonstrates the limited applicability of depth-based hydrogeological approaches in tectonically disturbed rock masses.

Spatial analysis (Fig. 3) reveals localized high-productivity zones, indicating the dominant role of structural factors such as faults and fracture zones.

Both the North and South pits exhibit mosaic patterns of groundwater productivity, reflecting structural heterogeneity.

The results highlight the need for integrated approaches combining drilling data, pumping tests, and spatial analysis in mine dewatering design.

Funding

The study was conducted within the framework of a research project in the field of subsurface use under Contract No. KA-R-250804-1 dated August 4, 2025, entitled “*Integrated hydrogeological study of the southern flank of the Akssu–Zholymbet structural–metallogenic zone blocks M-42-12-G (51,66) in the Shortandy District of Akmola Region (Zholymbet deposit case study)*”.

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